

SOCIO-PEDAGOGICAL ISSUES IN DEVELOPING ACTIVE CIVIC COMPETENCE AMONG DEAF AND HARD-OF-HEARING CHILDREN

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Annotation. The article explores the socio-pedagogical challenges in developing active civic competence among deaf and hard-of-hearing children. It highlights the importance of fostering civic responsibility, legal awareness, and social participation in this group through targeted educational methods. The research emphasizes the need for inclusive pedagogical approaches and comprehensive training programs to empower these children, ensuring their active involvement in societal processes. It also discusses the role of specialized educational institutions and family support in shaping their civic skills and preparing them for independent social life.

Keywords: greeting, deaf and hard-of-hearing children, civic competence, personal etiquette, spirituality, worldview.

Civic Education and the Formation of Active Citizenship in Hearing-Impaired Students

Today, identifying and implementing effective mechanisms for fostering patriotism, active citizenship, and responsibility among youth is of urgent importance. The strength of a state is directly linked to the legal and financial literacy of its population, as well as their socio-political engagement. When a person begins to feel a need to reject indifference toward surrounding events, only then can they become an active member of society. A person cannot fully develop as an individual, achieve economic stability, or maintain psychological balance in isolation. Social partnership and community are essential. Every society, in turn, functions within established laws, and individuals demonstrate their agency within the framework of these laws. If a citizen does not remain indifferent to surrounding events and acts in ways that benefit both themselves and others, they can be described as an active citizen.

Citizenship reflects, on one hand, a person's independence within society and, on the other hand, their participation in societal and state affairs. It is based on the idea of solidarity. Accordingly, the following characteristics represent key aspects of citizenship:

- awareness and practical application of one's rights;
- recognition and respect for the rights of others;
- personal responsibility and accountability for one's actions;
- understanding of one's legal and moral obligations to the state and society;

the principle of equal rights for all citizens;

objective and critical thinking toward social realities, based on moral-ethical and legal standards;

the ability to communicate with government, other citizens, and public organizations as a citizen.

Active citizenship involves active participation in public life, informed decision-making, and the protection of one's rights and interests.

Improving the methodology for strengthening the legal literacy of hearing-impaired students—particularly through developing their communication skills and shaping them into active citizens—is a topic that requires dedicated research. This is essential for preparing them for the labor market, enabling them to navigate various social relationships safely and effectively, and laying the groundwork for a secure and prosperous future. Since they often require assistance in legal matters, we planned experimental work to promote active citizenship among hearing-impaired students. For this, we studied a number of scientific works and historical sources on the subject.

The issue of civic upbringing was first addressed in ancient times by Socrates (469–399 BCE), who believed that although the process of upbringing is complex, it is necessary to help children grow into worthy individuals. His follower and student, Plato (427–348 BCE), laid the foundation for a civic education concept rooted in harmony among qualities that define a citizen. Aristotle (384–322 BCE) formed the conceptual basis of the idea of "obedience to law" and explained the positive influence of law on human upbringing. In Ancient Rome, children under the age of 14 were encouraged to swear oaths based on legal norms, such as: "I will not act unjustly toward any citizen, nor allow it to happen. If it does, I will report it, and I will act in court according to the law" [2].

Legal education and culture form the foundation of citizenship. If an individual seeks to be active but acts against the law, their behavior may lead to negative consequences for themselves and others. Therefore, in developing active civic competencies in hearing-impaired students, it is necessary to prepare them to act within legal norms. Lessons and educational sessions should teach them which behaviors are appropriate or inappropriate in public and interpersonal interactions.

Civic education plays a key role in shaping civic consciousness. Education and upbringing are inherently intertwined processes. Therefore, civic upbringing must be addressed alongside civic education.

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